

14 the spintronics toolkit, offering a new avenue for the design of low-power spintronics
15 multistate memories.

16 Keywords: magneto-ionics, magnetic textures, nanodevices, multistate memory, spin-
17 tronics.

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19 The energy-efficient manipulation of magnetic information carriers such as magnetic do-
20 main walls or skyrmions in spintronic devices is a cornerstone of novel magnetic-memory
21 concepts¹⁻⁴ and also have recently opened new perspectives for the design of spintronics
22 devices for non-conventional computing.⁵⁻⁸ Magnetic domain walls and skyrmions are the
23 magnetic textures showing the highest degree of technological development,⁹⁻¹⁴ while other
24 magnetic soliton structures have recently emerged,¹⁵⁻¹⁹ opening exciting new avenues for
25 low-power spintronics devices exploiting topology, chirality and the third dimension in mag-
26 netic nanostructures. However, challenges still remain such as the strong pinning potentials
27 experienced by domain walls in nanostructures and precise control of skyrmion nucleation
28 and propagation. In addition, there is a pressing need to reduce energy consumption, typi-
29 cally associated with the currents needed to create and propagate these magnetic textures.
30 In this context, going from current-driven to voltage-driven manipulation of magnetic solitons
31 is key to drastically reducing energy consumption in spintronics applications. The dynamic
32 control of magnetic anisotropy through voltage gating, either through charge or ionic effects,
33 has shown great potential to reduce switching currents in magnetic tunnel junctions^{13,14,20}
34 and to assist thermally-activated nucleation and magnetic field/current-driven motion of
35 chiral spin structures.^{13,14,21-26} However, a gate voltage does not act as a driving force for
36 propagation of domain walls, skyrmions and other spin textures. Therefore, pure voltage
37 control of the propagation of magnetic information carriers in devices remains a challenge.
38 A gate-controlled spin reorientation transition (SRT), is typically regarded as a homogeneous
39 process, where spins collectively react to the gate-induced reorientation of the easy axis of
40 magnetisation. This notion is largely due to the use of averaging techniques to measure the

41 effects of gating such as the anomalous Hall effect and the magneto-optical Kerr effect,²⁷⁻³¹ in
42 the absence of magnetic imaging. In this study, we show that an SRT between perpendicular
43 and in-plane anisotropy (PMA and IPA, respectively) can behave as a mobile non-collinear
44 magnetic structure, driven by the action of a gate voltage in a magneto-ionic device. We
45 show that SRT dynamics, including nucleation and propagation, can be controlled by gating
46 in a non-volatile fashion and that the motion of the SRT is detectable electrically through
47 the anomalous Hall effect (AHE). We show that when propagating uni-directionally along
48 a magnetic track, the SRT can fully sweep through the Hall cross with a total estimated
49 energy cost of 64 pJ and under gate-voltage pulses with lengths down to 20 μ s. This system
50 therefore opens new perspectives for enhancing robustness and energy efficiency in multi-
51 state spintronics memory devices. The voltage-driven transport of magnetic information is
52 in this case done by changes in the position of the SRT, which can not be erased by external
53 magnetic fields, a functionality that all the ferromagnetic-based memory concepts lack. This
54 feature constitutes a fundamental difference between a mobile SRT, a boundary between
55 two anisotropy states, and magnetic textures such as domain walls or skyrmions, which exist
56 within a material with homogeneous magnetic anisotropy and can be manipulated by mag-
57 netic fields and electrical currents via the spin-torque effect. In addition, the non-volatile
58 and analogue nature of the propagation of the SRT provides interesting perspectives for
59 the design of voltage-driven spintronics synaptic elements with a reduced energy cost per
60 weight-update operation compared to current-driven approaches.

61

62 The CoFeB-based Hall bar magneto-ionic devices used are depicted in Fig. 1 (a). Fig.
63 1 (b) shows the AHE response to the application of a gate voltage under 0.6 mT, which is
64 evidence of the large and reversible variations in the magnetic anisotropy that can be ob-
65 tained through magneto-ionic gating. In this system, the magneto-ionic mechanism relies on
66 the controlled oxidation/reduction of magnetic atoms at the ferromagnetic-oxide interface
67 mediated by the diffusion of oxygen species through the oxide layer under gate voltage.^{29,32}

Figure 1: Concentric motion of a SRT under constant gating. (a) Schematic of the magneto-ionic device. (b) AHE measurement while cycling the gate voltage between -11 V and $+11\text{ V}$ under a magnetic field of 0.6 mT . Kerr microscopy image series taken at zero magnetic field showing the nucleation and propagation of an SRT under a gate voltage of (c) -11 V , and the reversed effect under $+11\text{ V}$ (d). Dotted lines encircle the dominant PMA areas.

68 As shown in the leftmost Kerr-microscopy image of Fig. 1 (c), the initial magnetic config-
69 uration of the device is a multidomain state in the PMA regime. The constant application
70 of a negative gate voltage of -11 V progressively induces a substantial increase in magnetic
71 domain periodicity at the edges of the gate electrode, indicative of a critical reduction in
72 the PMA. Eventually, magnetic patterns are lost at the edges of the gate, which together
73 with the reduction in the AHE signal presented in Fig. 1 (b), indicates a loss of PMA.
74 Continuous gating up to 10 s shows the concentric motion of the SRT towards the centre of
75 the electrode, while the inner domain structure remains largely unaffected. For longer gating
76 times, the SRT profile continues to propagate towards the central part of the gated area and
77 a homogeneous IPA state can be achieved through the collapse of the SRT at the center of

78 the gate electrode (see SI section 7). As shown in the series of images in Fig. 1 (d), the
79 propagation of the SRT is a reversible process, under a gate voltage of +11 V the SRT moves
80 outwards until reaching the edges, reestablishing the initial PMA state. These results reveal
81 the complex dynamics behind the changes in the amplitude of the AHE under gating shown
82 in Fig. 1 (b). In contrast to the intuitive notion of a homogeneous anisotropy variation, the
83 gate-induced changes in the magnetic anisotropy from PMA to IPA occur in this case via the
84 nucleation of an SRT and its propagation, which creates two magnetic anisotropy domains
85 of PMA and IPA which contract/expand driven solely by a gate voltage. This is reminiscent
86 of the effects of a magnetic field on magnetic domains, which can expand and contract via
87 the motion of magnetic domain walls to achieve full alignment with the external field. As
88 in the case of magnetic domain walls, the position of the SRT can be moved back and forth
89 reversibly and its motion can be detected via the AHE. This reveals that an SRT can be
90 a magnetic information carrier entirely controlled by voltage instead of magnetic fields or
91 current.

92

93 Fig. 2 (a) shows a full view of a magneto-ionic device where the area outside the gate
94 electrode is in a saturated PMA state, while inside the gate electrode a multidomain pattern
95 was generated after gating (-10 V for 60 s, see SI section 2). Here, the complex magnetic
96 domain structure generated through gating is studied under increasing values of an external
97 perpendicular magnetic field. The area close to one of the Hall voltage contacts is highlighted
98 and shows three regions, delimited by dashed lines. The lower region shows PMA outside
99 the gate where magnetisation switches direction (0.2 mT - 0.78 mT). Above this region, at
100 the edge of the gate electrode, there is a gate-induced IPA state which is insensitive to the
101 magnetic field. In the top-most region, a PMA gradient extends for about 7–8 μm where
102 the magnetic domain pattern is progressively erased under increasing magnetic fields. These
103 measurements show that the SRT, unlike magnetic domains in the PMA region, can neither
104 be erased nor moved by the action of an external magnetic field, as the position of the SRT

Figure 2: Behaviour of the gate-driven SRT at the gate electrode’s edges. (a) Full view of a magneto-ionic device after the application of a gate voltage of -10 V, and detailed view of an area containing a SRT at the edge of the gate electrode as a function of a perpendicular magnetic field up to 2.54 mT. (b) Gate voltage cycling produces a damping in AHE associated to unsaturated areas along the electrodes’ edges, as shown in Kerr microscopy images, a significant recovery of the maximum AHE signal is achieved by extending the application of the positive gate voltage.

105 is fundamentally insensitive to the application of a magnetic field. The exposure to high
 106 magnetic fields could certainly be used to align the entire spin structure along any direction,
 107 however, a return to zero magnetic field will result in the recovery of the boundary between
 108 PMA and IPA, and therefore of any information stored in the SRT position. This adds a
 109 key functionality so far unavailable in ferromagnetic systems, a magnetic information carrier
 110 that is fundamentally robust against magnetic fields. Fig. 2 (a) also shows that there is a
 111 clear boundary between the IPA and PMA regions, which spans about 1-2 μm.

112 Although the SRT was driven back to the edges of the gate electrode in Fig. 1 (d) (outmost
 113 right image), the SRT was not fully annihilated at the lower edge of the gate electrode, as the
 114 remaining of a lower anisotropy state, visible in the form of a magnetic domain pattern with a
 115 higher periodicity, is still visible. This indicates that when the gate-driven change in easy axis

Figure 3: (a) Enhancement of the gating effects around local defects inside the ITO electrode under negative gate voltages. (b) Homogeneous gate-induced spin-reorientation transition under negative and positive gate voltages in a device containing a Pt gate electrode.

116 direction occurs via the motion of an SRT, non-saturated parts of this spin structure pinned
 117 at the edges of the gate electrode could cause a loss of magneto-ionic reversibility upon gate
 118 cycling. Fig. 2 (b) shows magneto-ionic gating where a progressive damping of the maximum
 119 AHE signal is observed from one cycle (-9 V/+12 V) to the following. The Kerr microscopy
 120 images presented in Fig. 2 (b) (images 1 to 4) confirm that the progressive loss in amplitude
 121 of the AHE upon cycling is due to an increase in the size of the IPA areas at the edges of the
 122 gate electrode with every cycle. Each image is taken at the PMA state reached after every
 123 three consecutive cycles of positive/negative voltage application, as indicated in the AHE
 124 plot (see SI section 2). However, a longer application of a positive voltage can drive the SRT
 125 back towards the electrode's edge, as shown in image number 5 of Fig. 2 (b). Therefore, the
 126 damping of the AHE signal upon cycling, which could be perceived as a critical deterioration
 127 of the device gating performance, can also be linked to the dynamics of a moving SRT and to
 128 the energy cost associated with the full annihilation of this spin structure within the device.

The origin of these edge effects is linked to defects and inhomogeneities located at the edges of the ITO electrode, as evidenced in interdigital transducers made of ITO.³³ ITO is a known ionically active material, its electrical and optical properties being linked to its oxygen content^{34,35} making it an excellent material for opto-electronic applications.³⁶ As the gating effect relies on oxygen diffusion under a gate voltage, a combination between the presence of an additional access to atmospheric oxygen at the edges of the ITO, variations in the thickness due to lithography defects and local electric-field inhomogeneities, contributes in this case to an enhanced effect of the magneto-ionic gating at the edges of the ITO electrode. This notion is supported by the observation of an enhanced effect of magneto-ionic gating also at defects located inside the gate electrode. Fig. 3 (a) shows the magnetic domain pattern under an ITO gate electrode containing superficial defects issued from a sub-optimal lithography process, the highlighted areas on the image indicate their locations. Prior to applying a gate voltage, these defects have no visible impact on the magnetic domain pattern, confirming they are superficial and do not extend into the magnetic layer. However, upon applying a negative voltage ramp, the magneto-ionic effect is visibly enhanced not only at the electrode edges but also at the defect sites. Fig. 3(a) also shows the domain pattern after applying a gate voltage ramp going from 0 V up to -16.5 V, revealing a significant reduction of the domain periodicity at both the electrode's edges and defect locations. These defect-related effects are accompanied by a strong degradation of the gate performance, evidenced as a strong increase in the leakage current (see SI section 3). Conversely, in typical devices where no defects are present inside the gate electrode, a critical degradation of the gate performance is often accompanied by structural damage at the edges of the gate electrode (see videos in the SI section 11). This is evidence of a locally enhanced electric field and ionic conduction area at defects in the ITO electrode, which enables the SRT nucleation at the gate electrode's edges.

The gate electrode's edge effects are suppressed when working at relatively low gate-voltages,

156 within the PMA window (see SI section 5) and when the ITO is replaced by a non-ionic ma-
157 terial such as Pt. Fig. 3 (b) shows the progression of a homogeneous quenching of the
158 magnetic domain contrast in the PMA state under a negative gate voltage, and its homoge-
159 neous recovery under positive gate voltages (see SI section 4). This reinforces the idea that
160 the ionic exchange between ITO and the gate structure is an important factor defining the
161 magneto-ionic dynamics and is therefore key to the nucleation of an SRT at the edges of the
162 gate electrodes.

163

164 Achieving an unidirectional motion of the SRT along a magnetic track, essential for its
165 use as an information carrier in spintronic devices, requires designating one edge of the gate
166 electrode as the dominant nucleation site. In samples with PMA close to the transition
167 towards IPA, the deposition of Ti/Au contact pads can induce a local anisotropy gradient
168 at the pad's edges, which can be evidenced by the reduction of the magnetic domain pe-
169 riodicity (see SI section 6). The influence of capping layers in the magnetic anisotropy of
170 CoFeB/oxide/capping-layer systems is well documented, the effects being highly dependent
171 on the capping-layer composition and thickness.³⁷⁻³⁹ In addition, it has been demonstrated
172 that local strain effects can be used to modulate magnetic properties by patterning of a pas-
173 sivation layer⁴⁰ in the vicinity of a magnetic wire. These combined features have been used
174 in this case to induce a local anisotropy variation to define a preferential nucleation point for
175 the SRT on the right side of the track, where a Ti/Au contact pad is located at a distance of
176 23 μm from the right-side edge of the gate, as shown in Fig. 4 (b). Using this design, the SRT
177 can be selectively nucleated on the right side of the track (Fig. 4 (a), image 1). Applying
178 gate voltage pulses of -5 V and 1 s progressively induces the unidirectional propagation of
179 the SRT towards the left side of the track (images 2 to 5) without the influence of any of
180 the other edges of the gate electrode. The images shown in Fig. 4 (a) correspond to the
181 difference between two images saturated at positive and negative magnetic fields, therefore
182 the light contrast under the gate electrode (dark contrast outside) corresponds to the PMA

183 areas. The AHE signal is recorded as the SRT moves across the magnetic track as shown in
184 Fig. 4 (c), the AHE values corresponding to each one of the Kerr microscopy images shown
185 in (a) are indicated, showing that the motion of the SRT can be followed by the change in
186 Hall voltage from full amplitude in the PMA state to a value near zero, in agreement with
187 a loss of PMA.

188 The SRT is a relatively broad magnetic transition, spanning several microns, much wider
189 than typical domain walls in perpendicular anisotropy materials, which are tens of nanome-
190 ters wide.⁴¹ Unlike domain wall motion, which yields a linear AHE response and allows
191 straightforward velocity calculation, SRT motion shows a highly non-linear AHE signal due
192 to its width being comparable to the Hall probe dimensions. This results in sensitivity not
193 only to position but also to the SRT's internal spin structure. SRT velocity can be estimated
194 by combining Kerr microscopy and AHE measurements (see SI section 10), as a function
195 of applied gate pulses. As shown in Fig. 4(d), increasing the gate voltage from -4 V to
196 -18 V causes the SRT velocity to rise by several orders of magnitude. This is reminiscent of
197 magnetic domain wall dynamics in the thermally activated creep regime, which originates
198 from interactions with pinning sites in a disordered medium,⁴² and it can be modeled as the
199 motion of a one dimensional interface in a two dimensional medium.⁴² In the present case,
200 as mentioned, the size of the SRT is comparable to the measurement probes of the device
201 and can not be considered a one dimensional interface. However, the mechanism behind the
202 motion of the SRT is not linked to the magnetic interactions with defects, but rather to the
203 ionic dynamics, which can be significantly affected by thermal activation.²¹ The exponential
204 dependence of ionic effects on the gate voltage applied is here translated to a highly non-
205 linear increase in the SRT velocity as a function of the amplitude of the applied gate voltage.

206

207 Leakage currents during SRT propagation in this device remain below 10 pA under a -5 V
208 gate voltage bias, corresponding to an estimated energy cost of 64 pJ for a full anisotropy
209 switch at the Hall cross (see SI section 8). This value represents the energy needed for full

210 potentiation or depression for synaptic operation, the cost per weight-update could then be
211 reduced by one order of magnitude within a realistic scenario in which the device is oper-
212 ated with ten intermediate magneto-ionic synaptic states, offering a major energy advantage
213 over current-driven spintronic synapses using skyrmion dynamics.⁶ Combined with com-
214 patibility for relatively short pulse-width operation, voltage-controlled SRTs offer a highly
215 efficient scheme for multi-state neuromorphic spintronic devices. In materials with strong
216 Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction, SRTs may become chiral objects and serve as mobile
217 points for skyrmion nucleation or reconfigurable chiral coupling between IPA and PMA
218 regions.⁴ As mobile magnetic carriers resilient to external magnetic fields, SRTs also offer
219 interesting perspectives for the design of devices for applications requiring robustness against
220 magnetic fields, where the conventional ferromagnet-based memory technologies have limited
221 applicability.

222

223 In summary, we present magneto-ionic devices in which a spin reorientation transition
224 can be nucleated, and propagated both radially and uni-directionally across a magnetic track
225 using a gate voltage. The propagation of the SRT over the Hall cross can be detected via
226 the AHE, offering multiple non-volatile and electrically readable AH resistance states within
227 the dynamic range of the device. The edges of the gate electrode play a crucial role in assist-
228 ing the nucleation of the SRT, while the SRT propagation velocity grows rapidly with the
229 magnitude of the applied gate voltage. The ability to reversibly nucleate and propagate an
230 SRT, a magnetic object typically confined in space by local materials engineering, therefore
231 adds a new mobile magnetic information carrier to the spintronics toolbox with interesting
232 perspectives for the design of new low-power functionalities in spintronic devices and robust
233 multilevel operation for neuromorphic hardware.

Figure 4: Unidirectional propagation of an SRT under gate voltage pulses. (a) Kerr microscopy imaging of the SRT propagating from right to left under gate voltage pulses of -5 V and 1 s. Color contours in image 1 show the Hall bar structure (pink), magnetic track (blue) and gate electrode (dark yellow). (b) Schematic representation of the device using the previous color scheme, with gold electrode close to the device on the right. (c) AHE signal corresponding to the images presented in (a). The SRT propagating within the 5 μm -wide center of the Hall cross corresponds to a significant change in Hall voltage. (d) Velocity of the SRT propagation for different gate voltage pulse lengths and amplitudes.

234 **Supplementary information**

235 Information about device fabrication, Kerr microscopy videos, further gating experiments
236 and description of the calculation of the SRT velocity.

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Figure 5: TOC